

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European
Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy
Transition and Markets

D3.4 Data Management Platform

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

DOCUMENT/ DELIVERABLE ID	D3.4 Data Management Platform
TYPE	OTHER
DISTRIBUTION LEVEL	Public
DUE DELIVERY DATE	31/12/2025
DATE OF DELIVERY	20/12/2025
VERSION	V1.0
DELIVERABLE RESPONSIBLE	AKKO
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DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	AUTHORS	DATE	CONTENT AND CHANGES
v0.1	Giovana Milenka Ciprián Herrera (AKKO)	20/11/2025	Table of Contents
v0.2	Giovana Milenka Ciprián Herrera (AKKO)	25/11/2025	First draft
v0.3	Giovana Milenka Ciprián Herrera (AKKO)	28/11/2025	Consolidated
v0.4	Marco Sacchet (LINKS) Babak Arbab Zavar (AAU)	03/12/2025	Revision
v0.5	Giovana Milenka Ciprián Herrera (AKKO)	16/12/2025	Release Candidate
v1.0	Giovana Milenka Ciprián Herrera (AKKO) João Catalão (UPO)	20/12/2025	Final Version

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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A sincere thanks to the colleagues listed in the "Acknowledgements" table for their valuable contributions during WP and Consortium Meetings, as well as open discussions, which significantly shaped the EU-DREAM Architecture. Their expertise and dedication were instrumental in formalising the content of this document.

ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Dynamic District Information Management Server
DAG	Distributed Ledger Technology
DDIM	Digital Twin
DevOps	Energy Management System
DLT	European Union
DT	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EMS	Grant Agreement
EU	General Data Protection Regulation
FAIR	JavaScript Object Notation
GA	JSON Web Token
GDPR	Natural Language Processing
IaC	Role-Based Access Control
JSON	Resource Description Framework
JWT	Query language for RDF
NLP	Structured Query Language
RBAC	Single Sign-On
RDF	Development and Operations
SPARQL	Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery
SQL	Directed Acyclic Graphs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the technical foundations and integration approach of the EU-DREAM **Data Management Platform**, developed under Task 3.4 during the period M4–M18. The goal of this task is to design how the platform will operate, how its parts will work together, and how it will connect to external systems that support the project's digital energy services.

The Data Management Platform is conceived as the central layer that enables different components of the EU-DREAM System to exchange information securely, consistently, and reliably. These components include the Data Platform (DP), Digital Twins (DT), Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), an NLP-based Intermediator, and other energy-oriented applications. By providing a structured, unified environment for data handling, the platform enables all these services to function smoothly as a single ecosystem.

The work carried out in Task 3.4 focuses on three main aspects:

1. It defines the overall architecture of the DP, ensuring that the design follows recognised industry practices, aligns with European recommendations, and remains consistent with previous work described in the system architecture D1.2 and Modular Platform D1.3 [1].
2. It explains how the platform's main components can be operated in practice, including Identity and Access Management (IAM), API Gateway, and DevOps-driven deployment environments.
3. It introduces the reference infrastructure that will later allow the EU-DREAM system to communicate with external systems, including sensors, Energy Management System (EMS), IoT devices, external databases, and the different Living Labs.

The platform is designed in a modular way, using clear interfaces and shared rules so that each part can evolve independently while remaining compatible with the others. The approach also supports scalability, allowing new services or larger volumes of data to be added when needed. Replicability is another key principle, meaning the platform can be deployed in different locations or Living Labs while following the same structure and guidelines.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable provides a comprehensive, consolidated, and implementation-oriented description of the EU-DREAM Data Management Platform developed under Task 3.4. Its purpose is to explain how the architectural concepts, functional components, interfaces, and security mechanisms defined in earlier stages of the project have been translated into an operational, scalable platform that supports the project's digital services.

The document describes how the platform is organised, how its elements interact, and how it can be deployed across different environments. It serves as the primary technical reference for any system or service that connects to the Data Management Platform. This includes the Digital Twin components, AI-based forecasting and optimisation services, the NLP intermediary developed in WP2, and the future consumer-facing energy services planned in WP4.

In addition to detailing the platform's structure, this deliverable also lays the Foundation for its deployment in the EU-DREAM Living Labs. It provides guidelines, integration points, and operational rules to ensure that all upcoming implementations are carried out consistently, securely, and with a shared understanding across all technical partners.

1.2. Scope and Boundaries

The scope of this deliverable covers all elements required to define, organise, and prepare the EU-DREAM Data Management Platform for integration and deployment.

Specifically, the scope includes:

- The complete architectural description of the Data Management Platform, detailing component responsibilities, data flows, interaction patterns, and the logical interfaces that link the platform with other project modules.
- The DevOps¹ and CI/CD processes govern how platform services are developed, tested, packaged, and deployed across different environments.
- The operationalisation of core cross-cutting services, including identity and access control, API management, secure communication channels, data pipelines, event-driven messaging, and distributed storage mechanisms.
- The definition of integration pathways with external systems, including energy management systems, IoT devices, sensor infrastructures, external databases, and edge-level components.
- A strategy for deployment within Living Labs, ensuring the platform can be reproduced, configured, and scaled consistently across different geographic and technical contexts.

The role of Task 3.4 within the final EU-DREAM architecture and software stack.

¹ DevOps is a set of practices that integrates software development and IT operations to improve collaboration, automate workflows, and enable faster, more reliable software delivery.

1.3. Relation with other Work Packages

Task 3.4 is positioned at the core of the EU-DREAM technical ecosystem and directly interacts with several work packages:

- WP1 provides system-level requirements, architecture guidelines [1], and component specifications. [2]
- WP2 develops the DT, AI models, and NLP-intermediator; these rely on the data platform for authenticated access, storage, and data exchange.
- WP3 implements data governance, DLT-based integrity, and interoperability services, feeding directly into the platform's data handling mechanisms.
- WP4 will consume the platform's interfaces to deploy consumer-centric energy services.
- WP7 validates the platform during Living Lab deployment and provides operational constraints.

In summary, Task 3.4 operationalises the architecture defined in WP1 and provides the infrastructure required for WP2 and WP4 services to run in real environments.

Figure 1: Interaction of Task 3.4 with Other EU-DREAM Work Packages

2. Reference Architecture of the Data Management Platform

The EU-DREAM Data Management Platform is designed as a modular, cloud-native, and secure digital infrastructure capable of integrating heterogeneous data sources, AI models, DT and a user-facing interface. System Architecture influences the architecture [1] and Modular Platforms [2]. In line with the project Grant Agreement and the FAIR Principles, the platform aims to manage and expose data in a way that makes it Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), supported by metadata, provenance, and standardised interfaces. [3], GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and modern DevOps practices.

2.1. Logical Architecture

At the logical level (Figure 2), the platform is composed of interoperable components with clearly defined responsibilities and communication patterns. The primary logical components include:

Figure 2: EU-DREAM System logical View (Source: LINKS)

2.2. Components

This section introduces the main technical components that form the EU-DREAM System and explains how they interact with the DT, DP, DDIM, and the Trusted Data Exchange Layer. In this task, the component descriptions support the definition of the overall platform architecture and guide integration and functional verification using tools from WP2, WP3, and WP4, ensuring scalability and replicability across LLs.

The EU-DREAM platform adopts a modular, interoperable architecture in which each component fulfils a clearly defined role within the Digital Twin, the Data Platform, DDIM, and the Trusted Data Exchange Layer. Together, these components implement the end-to-end data lifecycle from LLs, storage and processing, semantic integration, trusted exchange via DLT, and user interaction through the NLP-Based Intermediator.

Message Broker

The message broker is the communication backbone of the DT and DP. It provides asynchronous, decoupled messaging between orchestration services, agents and data services, enabling reliable, ordered, and scalable workflows.

In EU-DREAM, this role is implemented using Apache Kafka, a distributed event-streaming platform that connects simulation agents, AI modules, and support services. This component is an open-source distributed event streamer designed for high-throughput, low-latency message exchange and durable, replayable streams. [4]

Field	Content
Concrete Selected Component	Kafka Message Broker
Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic-based asynchronous communication between all DT services and data services. • Decoupling of orchestration, agents, and data services to reduce point-to-point dependencies. • Reliable, high-throughput delivery of events and messages with persistence and replay. • Supports multi-agent DT workflows through dedicated topics per workflow or per agent group. • Ensures ordered, durable, and replayable message streams across the DT pipeline. • Enables scalable coordination of simulation, AI, and data retrieval tasks using Kafka topics.
Main Logical Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orchestrator Topic workflow: commands and orchestration events. • Agent Topic: Task dispatch and result collection. • Data Topic requests and validated datasets responses. • Schema Registry: Management of message schemas to ensure consistent formats across all DT components.

Table 1: Message Broker Component Specification

DDIM

The DDIM Server is the semantic integration and knowledge management core of the EU-DREAM Data Platform. Its primary purpose is to transform heterogeneous data from LL and other sources into a coherent, interoperable, and ontology-aligned semantic layer that can be used by the DT AI models, simulation tools, NLP-Based Intermediator, and other Platform operators.

A central outcome of this process is the construction of knowledge graphs in Neo4j, where data is normalised, semantically enriched, and linked to the SAREF-based ontology model. This last one provides a shared semantic model to enable interoperability between IoT and smart-energy solutions. Because different sources often name similar concepts differently, the DDIM uses the ontology layer to align vocabulary and ensure interoperability across all data sources [5].

Field	Content
Concrete Selected Component	DDIM
Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ingest heterogeneous datasets via REST API and SFTP (CSV, JSON, BIM). • Parse, normalise, and integrate data into unified knowledge graphs, including schema mapping and unit/format harmonisation. • Apply ontology-based semantic relationships using SAREF [6]. • Manage entities, relationships and metadata in Neo4j, using nodes, relationships and properties to represent assets, measurements and contextual information [7]. • Maintain data history, update logs, and provenance records to support traceability and auditing. • Provide semantic query capabilities (GraphQL and SPARQL) for downstream components, such as DT workflows and the NLP-Based Intermediator.
Main Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST API: Data ingestion from external sources and access to linked data. • GraphQL API: Querying semantic data stored in DDIM. • SPARQL Endpoint: Access RDF/ontology-based semantic information. • Neo4j Connector: Storage and retrieval of graph entities and relations • InfluxDB Connector: Access to time-series data for semantic enrichment

Table 2: DDIM Server Component Specification

Orchestrator ETL/ELT

The orchestration ETL/ELT component automates, schedules, and monitors pipelines that move data from EU-DREAM databases into the DDIM. It ensures that raw or pre-validated datasets are periodically collected and delivered to the DDIM, which is then responsible for the semantic harmonisation and interoperability processes.

In EU-DREAM, this orchestration is implemented with Apache Airflow. For time-series data, Airflow can trigger ingestion tasks at fixed intervals or according to a custom schedule, optionally applying pre-processing before data is exposed to the DDIM. This allows the DDIM to receive time-aligned streams and integrate time-dependent measurements into the knowledge graph while preserving history, provenance, and semantic coherence [8].

Field		Content
Concrete Component	Selected	Apache Airflow
	Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automates the extraction of raw or structured data from databases (MongoDB, InfluxDB, PostgreSQL). Performs optional pre-processing steps such as validation, formatting, and consistency checks without performing semantic mapping. Schedules periodic, event-based, or batch ETL/ELT workflows using DAGs. Loads datasets into the DDIM ingestion interface for semantic interpretation. Tracks data provenance through timestamped DAG runs and execution logs. Manages retries, error handling, and monitoring of ingestion flows via the Airflow UI and the metadata database.
Main Interfaces	Logical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Databases (MongoDB / InfluxDB / PostgreSQL): Airflow orchestrate the extraction of raw or partially processed data from these stores. DDIM Ingestion API: Airflow schedule and delivers cleaned/validated datasets to the DDIM, which handles semantic alignment and graph creation. Airflow Metadata Database: stores workflow definitions, logs, run history, and execution provenance from ETL/ELT pipelines.

Table 3: Orchestrator ETL/ELT Component Specification

Databases

Multi-model data storage layer supporting structured, semi-structured, and time-series data across the EU-DREAM Data Platform. This layer stores Living Lab datasets, simulation results, metadata, and configuration information, and underpins the DT's data retrieval workflows. It also serves as an upstream data source for the DT. It provides high-performance data access, as described in the Logical View and Development View of the EU-DREAM System Architecture [1].

In EU-DREAM, this layer is implemented with:

- MongoDB: A document-oriented NoSQL database for heterogeneous data [9]
- InfluxDB: A relational database for structured, transactional data and platform metadata [10].

- PostgreSQL: a time-series database optimised for high-frequency measurements such as energy consumption and production [11].

Field		Content
Concrete Component	Selected	MongoDB, PostgreSQL, InfluxDB.
	Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Store heterogeneous data types from LLS in MongoDB. • Store structured relational data for system-level user accounts and platform services in PostgreSQL. • Store high-frequency time-series data in InfluxDB. • Enable efficient querying to support the DT workflows, analytics and monitoring dashboards. • Serve DDIM semantic ingestion via API queries and connectors. • Provide persistent storage for simulation inputs/outputs and historical datasets used by DT agents. • Support reliable retrieval operations accessed by the Data Handler during DT executions.
Main Interfaces	Logical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MongoDB API/Driver: Storage of heterogeneous datasets and metadata used by DDIM and DT agents. • PostgreSQL SQL Interface: Structured storage and querying for platform configuration, users and relational data. • InfluxDB Query API: High-frequency time-series access for DT models, DDIM, and analytics. • Data Platform REST/GraphQL API: Unified access to datasets accessed by DT components, DDIM and external tools. • Data Handler Interface: The DT infrastructure queries databases indirectly through the data handler during workflow execution.

Table 4: Databases Component Specification

Digital Twin

The DT infrastructure, more precisely the Digital Twin Orchestrator (DTO), is the core execution engine of the DT. It orchestrates workflows using an event-driven, stateless design. It decomposes workflows into tasks, dispatches agents via Kafka topics, and maintains their state externally. As described in the DT Infrastructure deliverable, the DTO coordinates simulation agents, AI agents, and data access components while ensuring modularity, scalability, and reproducibility [12].

Field		Content
Concrete Component	Selected	Digital Twins
	Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workflow parsing and decomposition into tasks. • Stateless orchestration with externalised context, so that workflow state is kept outside the orchestrator and can be recovered after failures • Task dispatching to Simulation, AI, and Data agents using Kafka

Main Interfaces		<p>topics, using correlation IDs to track each workflow.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation of intermediate results and triggering next workflow steps based on configuration rules. • Handling failures and retries, including task re-submission and timeout management. • Enabling multi-agent workflows to combine simulation, optimisation and data retrieval • Triggered via DT API from external components.
	Logical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orchestrator Topic: receives pipeline initiation requests and publishes orchestration commands. • Agent Topic: sends tasks to simulation/AI agents and receives their outputs. • Data Topic: Communicates DataTask requests to the Data Handler and receives validated datasets. • Redis: stores workflow state, context variables, and intermediate results for stateless execution. • DT APIs: external entry point to run workflows, check status, upload configurations and templates.

Table 5: DT Component Specification

DLT Interface

The Distributed Ledger Technology Interface (DLTi) is the middleware component that mediates all interactions between EU-DREAM modules and the permissioned blockchain network. Its primary role is to provide a trusted data exchange layer across all modules, ensuring the integrity, immutability, and verifiability of datasets used by DT, DP, and the services developed in WP4 [13].

The DLTi abstracts blockchain complexity, provides secure access control, performs Merkle Tree hashing, anchors data roots on Hyperledger Besu, and verifies proofs for dataset integrity.

Field	Content
Concrete Selected Component	DLTi
Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a controlled, secure gateway for all blockchain interactions (no other modules call the chain directly; access is permissioned and audited). • Perform Merkle Tree computation on incoming datasets (hashing, tree construction, root extraction) before anchoring. • Merkle tree processing. Roots and dataset identifiers on Hyperledger Besu for immutability and auditability, using smart contracts or dedicated anchoring transactions • Generate Merkle Proofs for later verification by Digital Twins or other modules. • Validate dataset integrity by comparing recomputed Merkle roots against on-chain roots. • Support GDPR, only hashes and identifiers are stored on-chain, while raw data remains off-chain.

Main Interfaces	Logical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure encryption, authentication, and secure-by-design data exchange, including TLS, VPNs, and key management mechanisms. • Hyperledger Besu RPC Interface: Used to submit Merkle Roots and retrieve them for verification. • DLTI API (Go-based): Exposes hashing, anchoring, and verification services to upstream modules. • Data Platform / Data Handler: Sends raw datasets to DLTI for anchoring and later queries integrity proofs during DT executions. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MQTT Topics: Used for exchanging dataset batches, Merkle proofs, and validation requests in distributed testbeds.
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Table 6: DLTI Component Specification

NLP-Based Intermediator

The NLP-Based Intermediator is the conversational intelligence layer of the EU-DREAM architecture. It enables end-users to interact with complex energy data, Digital Twins, forecasting services, and optimisation routines using natural language, written or spoken. It serves as the main user-facing component of the multi-agent system, translating user intentions into precise system actions, retrieving data from the EU-DREAM Data Platform, invoking analytical tools, and delivering personalised, context-aware insights.

The Intermediator operates across three architectural layers: Interaction, Reasoning and Supervision, and Tool Invocation and collaborates with specialised agents such as the Supervisor Agent and Energy Insight Agent to ensure accuracy, safety, and transparency. Internally, it uses a multi-agent orchestration framework to coordinate multiple LLM-based agents, each handling a specific part of the task.

Field	Content
Concrete Selected Component	NLP-Based Intermediator
Main Functionalities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural Language Understanding (NLU): Interprets user queries in multiple languages, extracts intents, parameters, and entities, and resolves temporal and contextual references. • Conversational Dialogue Management: Maintains context across multi-turn conversations using semantic and episodic memory; supports clarifications and follow-up questions. • Reasoning, Planning: Uses agent-based reasoning to break down complex tasks into actionable steps, coordinating with DT workflows and analytics services. • Tool Invocation: Invokes data sources and analytic tools (InfluxDB, PostgreSQL, Neo4J, forecasting modules, Energy Insight Agent) through the Model Context Protocol (MCP). MCP is an open standard that enables LLMs to call external tools and data sources in a secure, structured way. • Personalisation and Adaptation: Tailors explanations and recommendations based on user preferences, device profiles, and LL-

Main Interfaces	Logical	<p>specific configurations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety, Policy and Privacy Enforcement: Supervisor Agent enforces data-access rules, privacy constraints (GDPR), and safe interaction policies. • Multilingual Support: Handles input/output across languages used in EU-DREAM • LangGraph Platform API: Exposes REST/WebSocket interfaces for chat and voice-based user interaction and orchestrates multi-agent flows. • Supervisor Agent Interface: Coordinates reasoning, ensures safety, and routes tasks to specialised agents. • Energy Insight Agent (MCP Server): Executes energy analytics and database queries through standardised tool interfaces. • External APIs: Weather services, unit conversion, and ontology lookup tools are used to enrich reasoning. • Authentication Layer: Integrates with EU-DREAM token-based authentication to enforce identity and access-management policies.

Table 7: NLP-Based Intermediator Component Specification

2.3. Infrastructure Architecture

The EU-DREAM platform is deployed on a modular, cloud-ready infrastructure that can run on edge nodes, local servers, or public or private clouds. It uses containers and orchestration tools so that services behave consistently across environments and can be moved or replicated easily. This addresses the requirements for a modular, scalable architecture that can be replicated across different locations and configurations [1].

The infrastructure follows cloud-native and security-by-design principles, meaning security controls are planned from the outset and implemented across all layers.

The infrastructure is designed to connect the EU-DREAM system with external systems such as EMS, IoT gateways, and sensor networks deployed in the Living labs [14, 1]. This connectivity is implemented through:

- Secure northbound and southbound APIs are exposed via the API gateway, which manages routing, authentication, and traffic policies between external systems and internal services.
- Message brokers and data ingestion components that handle real-time streams and batch data from Living Labs and other data sources.
- Network and VPN configurations to ensure reliable and encrypted communication between distributed sites [13].

Infrastructure resources are provisioned and managed using Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC). Configuration for services, networks, and storage is stored in version-controlled repositories and applied through CI/CD pipelines, ensuring that the same configuration can be reproduced across Development, Pre-Production, and Production environments.

Environment Model

The EU-DREAM infrastructure is organised into three main environments:

- Development (Dev)
- Pre-Production(Preprod)
- Production(Prod)

Each environment plays a specific role in the platform's lifecycle and supports different stages of testing, validation, and operation. This structure helps Task 3.4 move from early prototypes to stable, production-ready deployments in a controlled, repeatable way across the Living Labs.

Table 8 below summarises these environments, their main technical characteristics, and their purpose. It provides a quick reference for developers, integrators, and operators to understand where to deploy, test, and operate each component of the EU-DREAM platform.

Environment	Characteristics	Purpose
Development (Dev)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Runs on a Docker Compose-based stack for fast setup and teardown on developer machines or shared test servers. • Includes all core microservices with simplified configurations. • Automatically deployed with CI/CD when code is merged or pushed to development branches, using IaC definitions to keep Dev environments consistent with higher environments. • Supports isolated end-to-end validation of DT components, ingestion pipelines, DDIM workflows and backend services without impacting Preprod or Prod. • Mirrors the logical architecture from the System architecture deployment, but with minimal operational constraints to speed up debugging and testing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rapid prototyping and debugging for new features. • Local integration testing of services and APIs • Developer-centric experimentation before their promotion to Preprod.
Pre-Production (Preprod)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses Docker Compose, enhanced with secure secret management aligned with the IAM security architecture. • Deployment requires manual approval in GitLab CI/CD to avoid accidental promotion or unstable changes to this environment. • Integrates routing, security, and access policies equivalent to production by using APISIX and Keycloak and logging and monitoring tools with realistic configurations. These configurations include OAuth2/OIDC flows, RBAC, and API-level rate limiting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System-level integration testing across all core components • Validation of security, privacy, and data sovereignty policies. • Rehearsal environment for test deployment procedures, roll-back strategies, and monitoring dashboards. • Verification of the LL configuration before

Production (Prod)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports system-level compatibility testing for DTO, DP, DDIM, and AI/NLP services, ensuring that changes remain compatible with the DT and the data-sharing components. • Validates Living Lab-specific configurations and data flows before deployment in the Prod environment. 	<p>rollout to the actual LL infrastructure.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Runs on a complete Kubernetes cluster with high availability, horizontal scaling, and continuous monitoring for all services. • Secrets and sensitive configuration values are injected via a secret management solution and the Kubernetes CSI driver, allowing secure rotation, auditing, and strict access control. • Horizontal autoscaling is configured for compute-intensive workloads, such as Digital Twin simulations, AI-based optimisation workflows, NLP-driven interactions, and high-throughput data ingestion and streaming. • Ensures stable, secure connectivity with Living Lab EMS, IoT gateways, and sensor networks, using API gateway rules, VPNs or secure tunnels, and message brokers to manage real-time data streams. • Uses APISIX as the primary northbound/southbound API gateway, aligned with interfaces and usage policy enforcement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full-scale operational deployment of EU-DREAM services. • Real-time processing of LL data streams and execution of DT, AI, and NLP pipelines for end users and operators. • Enforcement of IAM, DLT-based provenance, and monitoring policies ensuring trusted data exchange and regulatory compliance. • Basis for evaluating scalability and replicability of the platform architecture across different LLs and future deployments.

Table 8: Overview of EU-DREAM Deployment Environments

2.4. Implementation Strategy

This chapter presents the implementation strategy and describes how the EU-DREAM platform is put into operation on real infrastructure, from the development environment to full production across the LLs. It uses the three environments described in Section 2.3 and applies the same technical patterns to each.

In practical terms, this strategy defines how to:

- Package each platform function as a modular microservice.
- Deploy these microservices on a cloud-ready infrastructure that can run on edge nodes, local servers or cloud environments.
- Connect services to external systems such as EMS, IoT gateways, and sensor networks while enforcing security, trust, and interoperability requirements.

The guideline principles for this implementation are:

- **Modularity**, the platform is built from independent components (DT services, AI modules, the NLP-based Intermediator, the DP and DDIM, the DLTi, the API Gateway, and the IAM service). Each of these components runs as its own service, with a straightforward API and minimal coupling to others. This makes it possible to develop, deploy, and update components independently, and to combine them differently in each LL if needed.
- **Scalability**: the same containers can run on small edge nodes or on larger cloud clusters. In Production, Kubernetes can scale services up and down depending on the workload. This allows the platform to support heterogeneous LL data volumes and computational needs without modifying the logical design.
- **Resilience**: the use of containers and orchestration tools makes the system robust to failures. If one instance of the service stops, another is started automatically. If a node fails, services are rescheduled to another node.
- **Security** is integrated from the start, meaning that access to all services passes through the API Gateway and the Identity and Access Management service, which uses OAuth2/OIDC, Single Sign-On, and Role-Based Access Control. On top of that, the DLT anchors proofs of data integrity, consent, and key operation, so that the platform can demonstrate where data came from and how it was used [2].
- **Interoperability**, the DDIM harmonise data from different sources using standard ontologies and data models. This means that data from different EMS and IoT systems can be understood and used by the same AI and DT services.

From an operational point of view, the implementation strategy can be seen as a step-by-step process:

1. Define and package services, meaning that each function is described as a containerised microservice with its configuration, dependencies and interfaces.
2. Describe infrastructure and services as code, meaning that all infrastructures are described using IaC templates, which are stored in version-controlled repositories—these templates are used in all environments, with minor adjustments for each LL.
3. Automate build and deployment: when code or configuration changes, CI/CD pipelines build new container images, run tests, and deploy them first to development, then to Pre-Production, and finally to production after approval. This automation aims to reduce manual work and ensure that every LL receives the same tested version of the platform.
4. Run in hybrid cloud-edge setups; for each LL, the platform components are divided between the cloud and the edge. The same architecture and container images are used, but the exact placement of components is tailored to local constraints such as bandwidth, latency requirements, or available hardware.

5. Expose and protect interfaces; all interactions with the platform are organised and protected. Interactions are grouped into three interface families. Northbound for user applications and external actors calling the internal services, Southbound for LL, EMSs, IoT middleware and local services and finally, east-west for internal traffic between microservices.

Across all three families, the API Gateway and IAM enforce authentication, authorisation, and traffic control, while the DLT Interface is used by selected services to add integrity and provenance. This step makes the platform accessible to users and external systems while maintaining its security and alignment with the Trusted Data Exchange Layer.

Modular and Cloud-Native Deployment Approach

In EU-DREAM, each primary platform function is delivered as one or more containerised microservices. A microservice is a small, independent service that focuses on a specific capability and communicates with other services via simple APIs [15]. This is different from a monolithic application, where everything is packaged and deployed together. With microservices, EU-DREAM can update or scale services independently.

Each microservice runs in a container, a lightweight, standalone package that includes the application and all its dependencies. Using Docker containers means the same service behaves the same way on-premises servers or in a cloud cluster. EU-DREAM uses Docker images as the standard packaging format, ensuring the same components can be deployed consistently across Development, Pre-Production, Production, and different LLs.

- **Modularity:** Each component has its own container and API. These can be updated or replaced without impacting others, as long as their interfaces remain stable.
- **Scalability:** Kubernetes can automatically scale services up or down using mechanisms such as Horizontal Pod Autoscaling, which dynamically adjusts resources to manage high-frequency data from the LLs. It supports heavy workloads, such as real-data DT simulation, AI forecasting, and semantic queries, which may require significant computing power [16].
- **Resilience:** Kubernetes performs health checks, restarts failed containers and reschedules workloads when a node fails, improving overall robustness.

All infrastructure and service definitions are treated as IaC. Networks, storage, Kubernetes resources, API gateway routes, and some AIM monitoring settings are described in declarative templates and stored in GitLab repositories.

Cloud and Edge Deployment Strategy

EU-DREAM must operate across heterogeneous Living Labs, each one with its own characteristics, capabilities, data availability, and technical limitations. Therefore, the implementation follows a hybrid Cloud-Edge strategy, meaning that some components run in the cloud, while others run locally within each LL, as defined in the System architecture deliverable [1].

The approach is simple: components that need high computing power and ample storage run primarily in the cloud, while components that need very low latency, direct device access, or local privacy control run on the edge in each LL.

- **Cloud Layer – Centralised, Scalable Processing:** The platform runs a stack of shared services. First, the core Data Platform is deployed with time-series, relational, and graph databases, semantic storage, the knowledge graph, and the DDIM semantic broker, including its data access APIs. These elements together provide common data management, query, and semantic interoperability functions used by DT simulation and AI agents, the NLP-Intermediator, WP4 services [2] [5].

The DLT network, as with DLTi, is also hosted in the cloud, anchoring dataset hashes and workflow evidence, and exposing integrity proofs to other components [13].

On top of these, AI-based tools and optimisation models run on large volumes of historical data and use cloud computing to execute models. The NLP-based Intermediator and EU-DREAM backend provide a single entry point for user queries and workflows to reach all underlying services.

To expose these capabilities securely, the API Gateway and IAM services are deployed on the cloud layer as the central access point, enforcing authentication.

When very tight real-time behaviour is required, this gateway can also host small DT components or rule-based logic locally, reducing cloud dependency [12].

- **Edge Layer – Local, Low-Latency Computation:** Each LL operates an edge gateway that acts as the local integration point between the EU-DREAM System and field systems. It collects data from EMS, IoT middleware, and smart meters. The Edge Gateway then applies control commands and set points from DT services back to these devices with low latency.
- **Hybrid strategy:** For each LL, the components placement can be adapted. A site with strong local infrastructure may host more on-edge services, while a site with limited resources may rely primarily on cloud services and a thin edge gateway. Because everything is containerised and defined with IaC, moving a service between the cloud and the edge does not change its internal logic; it only changes its deployment target.

API Gateway

The API gateway is the main entry point to the EU-DREAM platform. It provides a single access point for user applications, edge gateways, and external consumers [1] [2].

In EU-DREAM, the role is fulfilled by Apache APISIX, which is a dynamic cloud native API gateway that offers features like [17]:

- **Routing:** The gateway receives incoming HTTP/REST or gRPC requests and forwards them to the correct backend service.
- **Traffic management:** The gateway enforces rate limiting, quotas, and timeouts to prevent any single client or Living Lab from overwhelming backend services.
- **Security with IAM:** The gateway integrates with the IAM service. For each request, it validates OAuth2/OIDC tokens, verifies their signatures and expiry, and reads their roles and permissions [18].

- Monitoring and observability for microservices APIs: The gateway exports logs and metrics to the monitoring stack. This helps operators understand usage patterns and detect anomalies.

By concentrating all these features, the API Gateway keeps the rest of the platform simple. It ensures that policies are applied consistently across all LL, which is essential for a replicable architecture.

Authentication and Access Control

EU-DREAM uses Keycloak as its Identity and Access Management (IAM) solution. Keycloak is an open-source identity and access management server that provides central authentication, user federation, Single Sign-On (SSO), and fine-grained authorisation for web applications and RESTful services [19].

The platform supports:

- Single Sign-On (SSO): Users log in once via Keycloak and can then access all authorised EU-DREAM applications without re-entering credentials. Keycloak manages sessions and identity.
- OAuth2 / OIDC for token-based authentication: EU-DREAM APIs are protected using OAuth 2.0 access tokens issued by Keycloak. OAuth 2.0 is the industry-standard authorisation framework that allows a client to obtain limited access to an HTTP service on behalf of a resource owner. Backend services and the API Gateway only accept requests with valid tokens.
- OpenID Connect (OIDC) authentication: The platform uses OIDC to obtain user identity information. OIDC is a simple identity layer on top of OAuth 2.0 that allows clients to verify user identity and obtain basic profile information.
- Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): Roles are defined in Keycloak. They are encoded into tokens and evaluated by the API Gateway and backend services to decide which APIs and datasets each caller can access.

These mechanisms protect sensitive resources such as user preferences, household consumption and generation data, DT outputs, and DLT integrity proofs, while still allowing authorised actors to integrate with the platform.

Interfaces

This section clarifies how the EU-DREAM platform exposes and protects its interfaces; The goal is to organise all interactions in a simple way that fits the System architecture. All interactions are grouped into three prominent interface families: Northbound (Client and ecosystem interfaces), Southbound (LL and Edge integration interfaces), and East-West (Intra-platform service-to-service interfaces).

Across all of them, the API Gateway and IAM enforce authentication, authorisation and traffic control, while the DLT Interface is used by selected services to add integrity.

- **Northbound - User Application Interface**

The Northbound interfaces connect the EU-DREAM platform with external users. Typical northbound clients are the EU-DREAM Mobile App developed in task 4.4, Living-Lab-specific custom mobile apps, and other consumer-facing clients. It is exposed via the Gateway component, which acts as an API gateway in front of the EU-DREAM Backend, the NLP-based Intermediator, and the Digital Twin APIs developed in WP2. All requests from mobile apps and web clients are routed through this gateway and translated into REST or gRPC calls toward the appropriate backend services. In this way, client applications do not need to know where the services are deployed or how they are scaled; they only know the public API.

Access to this interface is governed by the Identity and Access Management (IAM) service (e.g. Keycloak), which issues and validates tokens and enforces role-based access control. The gateway applies these policies to every incoming request, ensuring that only authenticated and authorised users can trigger simulations, retrieve digital twin results, or manage preferences. Endpoints (hostnames, ports, paths) are centrally managed at the gateway level, while individual services focus on business logic rather than client integration concerns. Figure 3 shows the leading actors and flows involved in these northbound interactions.

Figure 3: Northbound Interfaces connecting user-facing and external applications to the EU-DREAM services via the API Gateway and IAM.

- **Southbound - Edge / Living Lab Interface**

Southbound interfaces connect the cloud-side platform with the LL and edge infrastructure. They are used by edge gateways, EMS, IoT middleware, and other local systems that provide operational data and receive control signals.

In the upstream direction, LL devices and systems send measurements and events to the Edge Gateway. The Edge Gateway aggregates or pre-processes this data and forwards it to the cloud through secure tunnels using protocols such as MQTT, Kafka, or REST. The data is then ingested into the Data Platform and made available to DT services.

In the downstream direction, DT services running in the cloud control compute, optimise, or provide recommendations. These results are returned via the same southbound path.

From a networking perspective, southbound interfaces link the EU-DREAM platform to the LL infrastructure. Figure 4 shows how the cloud and edge sides relate through these southbound connections.

Figure 4: Southbound Interfaces linking cloud-level control and data services with Living Lab edge gateways, devices, and local systems

- **East/West Interfaces – Service to Service**

East-west interfaces describe internal communication between microservices inside the EU-DREAM platform. They are not used directly by end users or devices, but rather by services that collaborate to execute workflows, exchange data, and update models [20].

Technically, east-west interfaces use a mix of internal REST/gRPC calls and message-based communication over Kafka topics. This follows the event-driven architecture described in the System Architecture and Modular Platforms deliverables [1] [2]

- **Security and Trust Integration**

The Security and Trust components are applied across all family's interfaces. Where protection mechanisms are built into the architecture from the beginning and cover the whole data lifecycle. Three components work together to provide this cross-cutting security and trust layer:

- The API Gateway acts as the single technical entry point for most northbound and external calls and, in some cases, for southbound and east-west traffic. This means that whenever a user application, an external market API, or an LL gateway calls the platform, the request first passes through the API Gateway. Only if the request is valid and complies with the configured security policies is it forwarded to internal services such as DT APIs, Data Platform endpoints or the NLP-Intermediator.
- The IAM service implemented with Keycloak manages identities, roles, and tokens for both human users and technical clients. Keycloak also contributes to a federated identity and trust framework.
- The DLT Interface provides an additional layer of trust for critical data exchanges. Instead of storing raw data on the blockchain, the DLTi computes Merkle Trees for datasets or event batches, anchors only the Merkle root and identifiers on a permissioned Hyperledger Besu network and keeps complete data off-chain in the Data Platform. The DLTi Interface is the only component that talks directly to the blockchain; other modules should go through the DLTi APIs [13].

3. Technology Choices and Rationale

The EU-DREAM platform follows a cloud-native, DevOps-oriented approach. GitLab CI/CD, Docker, Docker Compose, Vault, and Kubernetes form a coherent toolchain used consistently across the Data Platform, DT infrastructure, and the Rust Data Exchange Layer, which simplifies integration and replicability across Living Labs [2] [12] [13].

3.1. GitLab CI/CD

GitLab CI/CD is the main continuous integration and continuous delivery (CI/CD) service for EU-DREAM. Pipelines are defined as code in `.gitlab-ci.yml` files and run automatically when code is pushed or when merge requests are created. They implement end-to-end automation for build, test, and deployment across all microservices and data pipelines [21].

Key characteristics of Gitlab CI/CD in EU-DREAM include:

- Support for multi-service and microservice architectures, where each service has its own pipeline stages.
- Full traceability of commits, pipeline runs, artefacts and deployment status in a single interface.
- DevSecOps controls, such as integration with static and dependency scanning, are used where needed.
- Native integration of code repositories, CI runners and container registry, reducing the number of external tools.
- Secure management of CI variables and branches or tag-based deployment rules.
- Flexible deployment to Docker, Docker Compose and Kubernetes.

This choice fits the project because GitLab already hosts the repositories, and GitLab CI/CD integrates tightly with its runners and registry. This limits the number of platforms to operate on, simplifies user and access management, and centralises logs, artefacts, and pipeline definitions. GitLab CI/CD also offers native integration with Vault for secure handling of secrets [21].

3.2. Docker

Docker is used as the standard container engine to package all EU-DREAM services. Docker image bundles application code, libraries and operating-system dependencies into a lightweight, portable runtime that can run on any host with a compatible container engine [22].

In EU-DREAM, Docker brings several advantages:

- Portability and replicability: the same image runs in Dev, Preprod, and Prod environments and can be deployed across different Living Labs without modification.
- Modularity and interoperability: each component has its own container and exposes its functionality only through clear, documented interfaces such as REST APIs, gRPC, or message broker topics, which support independent deployment and updates.
- Simplified dependency management: dependencies are already installed in the Docker image and do not need to be installed on the host system.

- In terms of performance and resource efficiency, containers are lighter than complete virtual machines and start quickly.
- Support for caching and dedicated storage, Docker builds images as a stack of layers, one per instruction in the Dockerfile. These layers can be cached and reused across builds and services, speeding up builds and preventing disk saturation.

Docker is the most widely used solution with strong community support, rich tooling and tight integration with GitLab CI/CD and Docker Compose.

3.3. Docker Compose

Docker Compose is used for local and pre-production multi-container orchestration. It allows developers and integrators to describe EU-DREAM stacks in a single *YAML* file and to start or stop either the entire environment or selected services with a single command [23].

In EU-DREAM, Docker Compose is used to:

- Launch full-integration environments in Dev and Preprod without running a complete Kubernetes cluster.
- Reproduce realistic multi-service deployments in testing environments.
- Simplify debugging with integrated access to logs, environment variables, and container networking.
- Provide a simple way to test new versions of services together before promotion to Production environments.

Using Kubernetes directly for all environments would ensure tighter alignment with production behaviour. However, it would also increase complexity, potentially slowing early development and making the local test setup more complex. Docker Compose is lighter, easier to learn, and still compatible with the Docker and Kubernetes workflow used in EU-DREAM, making it a better fit for Dev and Preprod environments.

3.4. Vault

Vault is the central secrets management system for the EU-DREAM platform. It serves as a digital safe, storing and controlling access to sensitive data. In practice, Vault stores information such as API keys, database passwords, OAuth tokens and TLS certificates in an encrypted backend. Only authenticated users, CI/CD jobs, and services with the correct policy are allowed to read or write these secrets [24].

In the EU-DREAM platform, the vault is used to:

- Create separate secret namespaces for each environment (Preprod/Prod) and for each microservice or tenant.
- Ensure that secrets are never stored in code repositories, configuration files or container images.
- Inject secrets dynamically into GitLab CI/CD pipelines and into application containers at runtime.
- Manage secret rotation, leasing and revocation and maintain audit logs of access to sensitive information.

Vault was therefore chosen as a provider-agnostic, open-source solution that integrates well with GitLab CI/CD, Docker and Kubernetes and aligns with the security requirements and architecture.

3.5. Kubernetes

In Production, Kubernetes orchestrates all containerised workloads of the EU-DREAM platform. Kubernetes is an open-source system for automating the deployment, scaling and management of containerised applications [25].

In EU-DREAM, Kubernetes offers:

- Self-healing means that pods are automatically restarted or rescheduled in case of failure.
- Horizontal scaling, components can be increased or decreased based on load.
- Rolling updates, new versions of services can be deployed with limited downtime and roll-back options.
- Multi-tenant isolation: different LLs can run in separate namespaces, each with its own resource quotas and network policies.
- Security controls, pod security settings, network policies, and integration with IAM and API Gateway support the project's security-by-design approach.

Running the platform only with single-host Docker or Docker Compose would reduce operational complexity but would not provide the same level of resilience, elasticity, or tenant isolation. Therefore, supports the growth of EU-DREAM in terms of the number of pilots, data volume and users, and allows the platform to be deployed both on-premises and in the cloud.

Overall, the combination of GitLab CI/CD, Docker, Docker Compose, Vault, and Kubernetes provides a consistent, open, and replicable DevOps stack. It supports the modular architecture of the EU-DREAM data management platform, enables secure and automated deployments, and can be reproduced across LL.

4. Environment Structures and Deployment Workflow

This chapter describes how the EU-DREAM Data Management Platform is operated across its three controlled environments: Development, Pre-production, and Production. All three reuse the same modular, cloud-native architecture described in the System Architecture and Modular Platforms deliverables, but with different levels of strictness, scale, and operational rules [2] [1].

Gitlab CI/CD pipelines manage the process in these environments. The Pipelines are defined in `.gitlab-ci.yml` files and automatically build, test, and deploy services when code is pushed or when merge requests are created, following the DevOps strategy introduced in Section 2.4.

4.1. Development Environment

The Dev environment is where new features, fixes and integration changes are tried first. It mirrors the platform's logical architecture but uses lightweight configurations to ensure fast feedback cycles and basic monitoring and logging. The structure of the entire platform is preserved, while operational complexity is kept low [22].

In this environment, the verification of component interoperability is performed. Any modification made in any component is first deployed here. Initial checks of IAM and routing are also done with test realms and test clients.

The workflow starts when a developer pushes code or creates a merge request on a development branch in GitLab. GitLab CI/CD reads the `.gitlab-ci.yml` file, builds the relevant Docker images and runs unit and basic integration tests. If the pipeline succeeds, the new images are pulled on the Dev host, and the Docker Compose stack is updated.

The developer then validates the behaviour directly in Dev by calling APIs through APISIX with development IAM tokens. If a problem is found, the developer fixes the code and reruns the pipeline. When the behaviour is acceptable, the version is marked as *stable for Preprod* and becomes a candidate for the next environment.

Figure 5 shows this process. The same logic is expressed in the sequence below.

Figure 5: Development Environment Deployment Workflow²

² This diagram shows how changes pushed by developers are automatically built, tested, and deployed to the Development environment, where basic functional and integration checks are performed before a version is considered stable for promotion to Pre-production.

4.2. Pre-production Environment

The Preprod environment is the controlled gate between development and real operation. It reproduces the production architecture at a reduced scale, with complete security, routing, and data governance, while still allowing flexible selection of which components to deploy.

In this section, a validation scenario is a concrete configuration deployed in Preprod for verification. Each validation scenario specifies a particular subset of components that will be active, defines the configuration for these components and selects the input and output simulated data based on the simulated LL.

In this way, every scenario has a precise technical scope and a clear validation objective, such as verifying east-west access to the DP for NLP queries in task 2.4.

At the current stage of the project, all validation scenarios use a simulated Living Lab. Data stream, EMS behaviour, and edge gateways are emulated rather than coming from physical sites.

This simulated LL allows the team to validate end-to-end workflows and security controls without relying on a full deployment of the real LL infrastructure. When real LLs are connected in later WPs activities, they will reuse the same environment structure, CI/CD flows and scenario definitions.

Figure 6 shows this process graphically and follows the same structure.

Figure 6: Pre-production Promotion & Validation Workflow³

From a technical point of view, Preprod uses the same Docker images that will later run in the Kubernetes-based Production cluster, but still relies on Docker Compose for orchestration. For each configuration, a Compose file (or set of files) describes only the necessary components, along with their networks, volumes, and environment variables. Secrets such as database passwords, API keys and TLS certificates are stored and managed by the vault and injected at runtime.

APISIX and Keycloak are configured with production-like realms, clients, routes and plugins. APISIX routes external and selected internal calls and enforces rate limiting and logging, while Keycloak issues OAuth2/OIDC tokens and applies role-based access control for human users and technical clients [18].

A release candidate coming from Dev triggers a dedicated CI/CD pipeline for Preprod. The pipeline builds or reuses images, runs extended automated checks, and then pauses at a manual approval stage. Only after approval is the selected stack deployed, which prevents accidental promotion of unstable versions.

During execution, the team performs checks across both functional and non-functional aspects and provides adequate logging, metrics, and alerts. If these checks are successful for the intended scope, the version is considered ready to move to the Production environment. If problems appear, they are analysed, fixes are applied in Dev, and the same configuration is re-run in Preprod until the behaviour is satisfactory.

³ This diagram illustrates the controlled promotion of a stable version from Development to Pre-production, including manual release approval, deployment with Vault-managed secrets, and comprehensive validation before any Go/No-Go decision for Production is taken.

4.3. Production Environment

The Prod environment hosts the operational instance of the EU-DREAM platform. It is designed to support real Living Labs. However, in the current phase of the project, it is connected to a simulated LL setup, where data streams, EMS behaviour and user interactions are emulated. This simulated LL is used to verify that the architecture, components and DevOps processes can run in a realistic, always-on configuration and can later be reused for real LLs [2].

From a hardware and infrastructure perspective, production runs on a Kubernetes cluster. A Kubernetes cluster is a group of worker nodes that work together to run containerised applications and provide a unified environment for deploying and managing services. Each worker node can run several DT agents and data services in parallel. More nodes can be added if more workloads are introduced. If one node fails, Kubernetes reschedules the affected pods to other nodes, maintaining service availability [25] [1].

Operationally, all services are described as Kubernetes resources such as Deployments, Services, Ingresses, Jobs, and stored in version-controlled repositories. CI/CD pipelines apply these manifests or Helm charts to the cluster, which makes Production deployments reproducible and traceable.

Horizontal Pod Autoscaling is configured for components with variable load, such as DT simulation, AI agents, the NLP-based Intermediator and ingestion pipelines. When data rate requests increase, Kubernetes starts additional pods for these services, and when the load decreases, pods are scaled down.

Secrets and sensitive configuration values are injected into pods at runtime from Vault and Kubernetes secret mechanisms. This ensures that passwords, keys, and tokens are not embedded in Docker images or plaintext manifests, and can be rotated without rebuilding containers.

All external traffic and a large part of the internal API calls pass through APISIX, which serves as the API Gateway in Production. APISIX validates tokens issued by Keycloak, enforces routing rules and rate-limiting policies, and exposes a consistent API surface, while Keycloak provides SSO, OAuth2/OIDC tokens, and role-based access control.

Figure 7 shows the overall deployment process.

Figure 7: Production Deployment Workflow⁴

⁴ This diagram depicts the Production deployment process on Kubernetes, where an approved release is rolled out with Vault CSI-backed secrets, monitored for stability, and rolled back if any critical issues are detected.

5. CI/CD Pipeline Structure

The CI/CD pipeline links all three previously mentioned environments, ensuring that every modification is built, tested, and deployed in the same way across all LLs [1] [2].

The CI/CD pipeline implemented in EU-DREAM defines the complete lifecycle of service delivery, from source code to production deployment. It ensures that every platform component is delivered through a controlled, verifiable, and repeatable process.

The pipeline is organised into a sequence of stages: Build, Test, and Deployment. Each stage uses shared GitLab CI/CD templates so that all services follow the same rules [21].

5.1. CI/CD Stage-by-Stage

The EU-DREAM CI/CD pipeline defines a common path for every service, from a code change in GitLab to a running component across the Dev, Pre-Production, and Production environments. Each change passes through a Build Stage, Test Stage, and one or more deployment stages, starting with the Development deployment.

These Ideas are implemented in the GitLab pipeline and Docker compose. The pipeline is defined in the root `.gitlab-ci.yml` file.

```
# =====
# CI/CD Docker Pipeline
# =====

workflow:
  rules:
    - if: '$CI_PIPELINE_SOURCE == "merge_request_event"'
    - if: $CI_COMMIT_BRANCH
      when: always
      exists:
        - docker-compose.yml
        - docker-compose.preprod.yml

default:
  image: docker:28.4.0

variables:
  DOCKER_HOST: unix:///var/run/docker.sock
  DOCKER_BUILDKIT: "1"
  COMPOSE_DOCKER_CLI_BUILD: "1"

stages:
  - build
  - test
  - deploy_dev
  - deploy_preprod
```

Figure 8: Top-level GitLab CI/CD configuration in `eu-dream-dp`, defining the common stages and Docker-based execution context for all jobs.

- build: turn source code into Docker images for all services
- test: start the stack and verify that services work together
- deploy_dev: deploy the validated stack to the shared Development environment
- deploy_preprod: deploy a near-production configuration to the Pre-Production environment.

Build Stage

The Build Stage is responsible for transforming raw source code into a fully packaged, versioned, and reproducible Docker image, serving as the artefact for all subsequent stages of the CI/CD pipeline.

The main goal of this stage is to produce deterministic and traceable images. Each image embeds metadata such as the Git commit SHA, semantic version, build timestamp and GitLab pipeline ID. This allows us to see precisely which code and configuration are running in each environment.

In the GitLab configuration, this is implemented by the *docker-build* job.

```
# =====
# BUILD STAGE (Runner: AIM-2)
# =====
docker-build:
  stage: build
  tags:
    - runner-dev-aim-2
  script:
    - echo " Building Docker images..."
    - docker compose build --no-cache
    - echo "Build completed successfully."
```

Figure 9: Build job in the CI/CD pipeline, calling *docker-compose-build* to build all Data Platform services from the repository.

Using *docker-compose build* ensures that every service defined in *docker-compose.yml* is built consistently.

Apply secure-by-design principles: For services where the project controls the Dockerfile, the build stage follows a secure-by-design approach. The containers are configured to run as unprivileged users rather than *root*. The final runtime image is kept as small as possible, meaning it contains only the application and its runtime dependencies, while compilers, build tools, and temporary build artefacts remain in the builder stage. Unnecessary operating system packages, debugging tools, and sample data are removed, reducing the number of components that could contain vulnerabilities. Finally, explicit versions are used for base images and Python dependencies, making the resulting images deterministic and reproducible.

Figure 10 illustrates how these principles are applied to a Python-based service such as the Cleanwatts ingestion component.

```

1  # ---- Builder stage: install dependencies with uv -----
2  FROM python:3.12-slim AS builder
3
4  # Install build utilities only in the builder image
5  RUN apt-get update \
6      && apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends curl build-essential \
7      && curl -Lsf https://astral.sh/uv/install.sh | sh \
8      && rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/*
9
10 ENV PATH="/root/.local/bin:${PATH}"
11
12 WORKDIR /app
13
14 # Copy dependency descriptors first to leverage Docker layer cache
15 COPY pyproject.toml uv.lock requirements.txt ./
16
17 # Create an isolated virtual environment and install Python deps
18 RUN uv venv /opt/venv \
19     && . /opt/venv/bin/activate \
20     && uv pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt
21
22 # Copy the application source code
23 COPY src/ ./src
24 COPY main.py .
25
26 # ---- Runtime stage: minimal, non-root image -----
27 FROM python:3.12-slim AS runtime
28
29 # Create non-root user
30 RUN useradd --create-home appuser
31
32 # Copy only the venv and app code from the builder stage
33 COPY --from=builder /opt/venv /opt/venv
34 COPY --from=builder /app /app
35
36 # Activate virtualenv by default
37 ENV PATH="/opt/venv/bin:${PATH}"
38 WORKDIR /app
39
40 # Expose service port
41 EXPOSE 8787
42
43 # Drop privileges
44 USER appuser
45
46 # Entrypoint
47 CMD ["python", "main.py"]
48

```

Figure 10: Multi-stage Dockerfile used for a Data Platform service (e.g. Cleanwatts data ingestion)

This approach separates the build responsibilities from the runtime responsibilities. The Build stage calls docker-compose build, and Docker Compose uses these Dockerfiles to create hardened images.

Security and quality checks during the build stage: The CI/CD design foresees additional checks during the build, even if some are introduced gradually. Performing SAST/SCA are Gitlab's security template that can be included so that source code and dependencies are scanned for known vulnerabilities [21], additionally tools like Hadolint can detect insecure or inefficient instructions [26], and finally image tagging with a commit SHA and semantic version and pushed to a GitLab Container Registry namespace, allows deployments, including in the Kubernetes-based Production environment, to always refer to an immutable image.

In summary, the Build stage produces a reproducible, hardened set of Docker images that become the single source of truth for all subsequent stages of the CI/CD pipeline.

Test Stage

The Test stage answers to the question that if we start the services and stacks built in the build stage do they actually run, and are their main entry points reachable?, this means checking that the containerised components defined in the repository can be started together with Docker Compose, that their exposed HTTP endpoints respond correctly, and that core services can communicate with each other over the internal network.

In the context of the EU-DREAM Data Platform, this means checking that Docker images produced in the Build stage can be started with Docker Compose, that the main HTTP endpoints respond correctly, and that core services can communicate over the internal Docker network.

The first building block of the Test stage is the docker-test job, defined at the repository root. Figure 11 below shows how this job brings up the entire stack, runs a smoke test, and then tears it down again.

```

40 # =====
41 # TEST STAGE (Runner: AIM-2)
42 # =====
43 docker-test:
44   stage: test
45   tags:
46     - runner-dev-aim-2
47   script:
48     - echo "Running integration tests..."
49     - docker network create livinglabplatform_default || true
50     - docker compose up -d
51     - sleep 10
52     - docker ps
53     - echo "Tests completed."
54     - docker compose down
55

```

Figure 11: GitLab CI job docker-test bringing up the complete stack in detached mode, performing a smoke check, and tearing it down again.

Here, the job first ensures that the expected Docker network exists, then starts all services defined in *docker-compose.yml*. It lists running containers. If any service crashes immediately, it will appear with an exited status, and the job log will reveal the problem. Finally, the stack is stopped and removed.

In addition to this smoke test, the Test stage comprises three complementary layers of verification, unit tests, integration and connectivity checks, and optional security and licence checks.

Unit Tests: The role of the Unit tests is to verify that internal functions behave as expected (e.g. in eu-dream-dp, tests are stored alongside services, *main_test.py* next to *main.py* in the Cleanwatts ingestion folder, and CI jobs use tools like *pytest* to run them.) [27]

Integration and connectivity Tests: To verify that services work together as a system, the repository provides a more complete script, *test_services.sh*, intended to be run after *docker-compose up* in the Dev environment. It checks both external endpoints and internal service-to-service connectivity. Figure 12 shows the beginning of this script, where the primary HTTP endpoints are defined and tested.

```

1  #!/bin/bash
2  # =====
3  # EU-DREAM Platform - Docker Service Test Script (DEV Edition)
4  # Full connectivity and health verification
5  # =====
6
7  LOG_FILE="test_results_dev_containers.log"
8
9  # Clear previous log file
10 echo "" > "$LOG_FILE"
11
12 echo ""
13 echo "===== " | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
14 echo "EU-DREAM PLATFORM - DOCKER SERVICE TEST (DEV MODE)" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
15 echo "===== " | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
16 echo "" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
17
18 # 1 - Wait for containers to stabilize
19 echo "[0] Waiting 20 seconds for containers to initialize..." | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
20 sleep 20
21 echo "" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
22
23 # 2 - Check Docker containers status
24 echo "[1] Checking Docker containers..." | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
25 docker compose ps -a | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
26 echo "" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
27
28 # 3 - Define HTTP endpoints to test
29 declare -A endpoints=(
30   ["Data Platform API (FastAPI)"]="http://localhost:8001"
31   ["Mongo Express"]="http://localhost:8081"
32   ["Front UI"]="http://localhost:3001"
33   ["Web Application"]="http://localhost:8000"
34   ["Kafka UI"]="http://localhost:8082"
35   ["InfluxDB"]="http://localhost:8086/health"
36   ["Grafana"]="http://localhost:3000"
37   ["PhpMyAdmin"]="http://localhost:8888"
38   ["Cleanwatts Data Ingestion"]="http://localhost:8787"
39 )
40
41 # 4 - Test external HTTP endpoints
42 echo "[2] Checking HTTP endpoints..." | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
43 for name in "${!endpoints[@]}"; do
44   url=${endpoints[$name]}
45   echo -n "Testing $name -> $url ... " | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
46   code=$(curl -o /dev/null -s -w "%{http_code}" "$url")
47   if [[ $code -ge 200 && $code -lt 400 ]]; then
48     echo "OK ($code)" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
49   else
50     echo "FAILED ($code)" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
51   fi
52 done

```

Figure 12: Extract from `test_services.sh`, which waits for container start-up, logs Docker status, and checks HTTP endpoints for the primary services.

Then it continues with internal communication checks to verify that containers can communicate with each other across the Docker network. Figure 13 below shows how these internal tests are defined using Python snippets executed inside containers.

```
# 5 - Internal communication checks between containers
echo "[3] Checking internal communication..." | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"

declare -A internal_tests=(
  ["Logger -> MongoDB"]="docker exec -i logger python3 -c 'import socket; socket.create_connect:
  ["FastAPI -> MongoDB"]="docker exec -i data_platform_api python3 -c 'import socket; socket.cri
  ["FastAPI -> InfluxDB"]="docker exec -i data_platform_api python3 -c 'import socket; socket.ci
  ["GraphQL -> Kafka"]="docker exec -i graphql-api-python python3 -c 'import socket; socket.cre:
  ["Kafka to MongoDB -> MongoDB"]="docker exec -i kafka-to-mongodb python3 -c 'import socket; s:
  ["Kafka to InfluxDB -> InfluxDB"]="docker exec -i kafka-to-influxdb python3 -c 'import socket
)
```

Figure 13: Internal connectivity checks are executed inside containers to verify that each service can open a TCP connection to its dependencies.

Optional security checks and licence compliance can be attached to the test stage without interrupting day work, see Figure 14 as an example.

```
--
56 cleanwatts-security-scan:
57   stage: test
58   image: python:3.12-slim
59   tags:
60     - runner-dev-aim-2
61   before_script:
62     - apt-get update && apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends curl
63     - pip install --no-cache-dir pip-audit safety bandit
64   script:
65     - cd clean_watts_ingestion
66     - echo "Running dependency vulnerability scan (pip-audit)..."
67     - pip-audit -r requirements.txt || true
68     - echo "Running licence / vulnerability check (safety)..."
69     - safety check -r requirements.txt || true
70     - echo "Running static code analysis (bandit)..."
71     - bandit -r . -ll || true
72   allow_failure: true
73   rules:
74     - if: '$CI_COMMIT_BRANCH'
75
76
```

Figure 14: CI job cleanwatts-security-scan executing dependency and static-code security checks.

The Test stage ensures that the stack starts correctly, that the primary services respond as expected, that containers can communicate with their dependencies, and that basic security issues are identified early. This creates a safety net before any change is deployed into shared environments.

Dev Deployment stage

The Development Stage provides a shared, always-up-to-date environment where all services from the repository run together and can be exercised by developers and integrators. Whenever the `dev` branch changes, the Dev environment is refreshed to reflect the latest integrated state of the repository.

The `docker-deploy-dev` job implements this behaviour. Figure 15 below shows the job definition that rebuilds and redeploys the stack on the Dev runner.

```

56 # =====
57 # DEPLOY DEV (Runner: AIM-2)
58 # =====
59 docker-deploy-dev:
60   stage: deploy_dev
61   tags:
62     - runner-dev-aim-2
63   environment:
64     name: Dev
65     url: $DEV_URL
66   before_script:
67     - echo "Creating DEV network..."
68     - docker network create livinglabplatform_default || true
69   script:
70     - echo " Deploying Docker Compose for DEV..."
71     - docker compose pull
72     - docker compose down
73     - docker compose up -d --build
74     - echo " Checking container status..."
75     - |
76       if docker compose ps --filter "status=exited" | grep -q "Exit"; then
77         echo " Error: Some containers failed to start in DEV"
78         docker compose ps
79         exit 1
80       else
81         echo " All DEV containers are running correctly!"
82       fi
83   rules:
84     - if: '$CI_COMMIT_BRANCH == "dev"'
85     when: always
86

```

Figure 15: Dev deployment job `docker-deploy-dev`, rebuilding and redeploying the full stack whenever the `dev` branch is updated and verifying that all containers remain healthy.

The job ensures that the Dev network exists, pulls updated images, stops any previous stack, and starts all services again in detached mode. Then it checks whether any container has exited; if so, the job fails and prints the container list, making it clear that Dev is not in a good state.

The services themselves are described in `docker-compose.yml`. Figure 16 below shows an extract with the Cleanwatts ingestion service and a FastAPI-based API as examples of how services are declared and attached to the shared network.

```

120 # =====
121 # CLEANWATTS DATA INGESTION
122 # =====
123 cleanwatts-data-ingestion:
124   build: ./clean_watts_ingestion
125   container_name: cleanwatts-data-ingestion
126   restart: unless-stopped
127   ports:
128     - "${CLEANWATTS_PORT:-8787}:8787"
129   networks:
130     - livinglabplatform_default
131
132 # =====
133 # DATA PLATFORM API (FastAPI)
134 # =====
135 data_platform_api:
136   build: ./data_platform_api
137   container_name: data_platform_api
138   restart: unless-stopped
139   ports:
140     - "${FASTAPI_PORT:-8001}:8001"
141   env_file:
142     - .env
143   depends_on:
144     mongodb:
145       condition: service_healthy
146   networks:
147     - livinglabplatform_default
148

```

Figure 16: Cleanwatts ingestion service and a FastAPI-based API, both are built from the repository and attached to the shared Dev network.

When the Dev deployment job finishes, all these components run together and can be accessed using the ports and URLs defined in the compose file. This provides the project with a realistic yet controlled environment for experimentation and debugging.

In summary, the Dev deployment stage ensures that there is always a living, integrated version of the repository that matches the dev branch. This environment serves as a common playground where ideas can be tested, issues reproduced, and features prepared before they are considered for Pre-Production.

6. Security Considerations

The security architecture of the EU-DREAM platform follows a zero-trust approach and security-by-design principles [1] [13]. This means that security requirements are considered from the platform's initial design rather than added later as patches, and that no service, user, network, or environment is implicitly trusted.

Every interaction must be authenticated, authorised, encrypted, and auditable.

6.1. Zero-Trust Architecture

Zero trust is a security model based on the principle "never trust, always verify", where no user, device, or service is trusted by default, even if it is inside the network perimeter [28] or inside a Kubernetes cluster. Instead, each request must prove its identity and must be checked against explicit policies before access is granted. [2].

Zero-trust principles are applied to EU-DREAM components. This means that data should always flow through controlled paths, and critical operations, such as accessing LL telemetry, triggering DT workflows, or anchoring data on the DLT, must be verifiable and traceable.

No implicit trust in any service or network

Nothing inside the internal network is often considered trusted. The EU-DREAM platform explicitly avoids this assumption. Every workload is treated as potentially untrusted and must prove its identity and authorisation before accessing data or calling other services.

- All microservices are onboarded with explicit identities and security policies. An identity can be a user account, a technical client, or a service account that is recognised by the IAM service (Keycloak). The platform does not rely on source IP addresses or on internal network labels to make trust decisions.
- Kubernetes clusters, network policies, and API Gateway rules are used to separate LLs and EU-DREAM Components. This segmentation limits the radius of incidents, but it is not the only defence line; it is always combined with authentication and authorisation at the application level.
- Access decisions are always based on authenticated identities, user accounts, technical clients, or service accounts, and on explicit policy rules, such as RBAC roles and DLT-based data usage constraints.

This approach focuses on protecting assets and workflows rather than static network perimeters. It also allows EU-DREAM to enforce the same security level across heterogeneous LLs, even when their local networks and devices differ.

Mandatory authentication and authorisation for every request

Every interaction with the platform must present a verifiable identity and pass an authorisation check. [2]

- For user-facing calls, northbound interfaces, and web and mobile applications, authentication is handled by the IAM service (Keycloak), and tokens are obtained via OAuth2/OIDC. The API Gateway validates these tokens and applies role-based access control before forwarding any request to DT APIs, Data Platform endpoints or the NLP-based Intermediator [2] [13] [29] [17].
- For service-to-service calls and east-west interfaces, internal clients use technical identities and tokens issued by the IAM, or mTLS certificates, to authenticate before accessing internal APIs or Kafka topics.
- For southbound interfaces, LL gateways and EMS connectors authenticate when sending data to the platform and when receiving control signals, so that only authorised LL instances can interact with DT and optimisation workflows [13].

Authorisation follows a role-based model enriched with specific permissions. These permissions are encoded into tokens by Keycloak and are evaluated by the API Gateway and backend services to determine which APIs and datasets each caller can access [18].

The DLT layer complements these mechanisms by storing immutable proofs about data and workflows. Instead of logging only in databases, selected actions are anchored as hashes on the permissioned blockchain. This makes it possible to audit later which authorised actions were performed on protected datasets [13].

End-to-end encryption

To protect data while it travels between components, all communication channels are encrypted, both inside and outside the cluster. Encrypting data "in transit" ensures that even if someone can listen on the network, they cannot read or modify the messages helpfully.

External access to platform APIs, dashboards, and LL interfaces is protected with TLS, following best practices for HTTPS endpoints.

- External access to platform APIs, dashboards, and LL interfaces is always protected by TLS, the standard protocol used by HTTPS. TLS provides confidentiality, integrity, and server authentication. In EU-DREAM, TLS is enforced at the API Gateway, and mTLS is used for internal exchanges, especially between the API Gateway, DT services, the Kafka broker, and Data Platform microservices.
- Internal communication between critical services uses mTLS, especially between the API Gateway. With mTLS, both sides present certificates and verify each other, so that a DT service can be sure it is really talking to the authorised Kafka broker, and not to a fake service.
- Connections between DLT validator nodes and the DLTi follow the same principle. Only authenticated nodes may join the permissioned blockchain network, and all traffic between them is encrypted [13].

Together, mandatory encryption and mutual authentication make sure that data cannot be read or modified in transit, even on internal networks.

6.2. EU-DREAM API Gateway – Identity Provider Exchange Flow

The API Gateway and IAM together implement a standard OpenID Connect (OIDC) authentication and authorisation pattern. The gateway, implemented with Apache APISIX, acts as a policy enforcement point for all exposed APIs, while Keycloak acts as the OIDC-compliant Identity Provider [17] [29].

The process is divided into three main stages:

1. Sign-in flow, where the user proves who they are
2. Access flow, where the gateway exchanges the login result for tokens and uses them to call the EU-DREAM services
3. Session flow, where later requests reuse an existing session or token so that the user does not have to log in again for every call

This section describes these three stages at a high level, independent of any specific vendor. It aligns them with the high-level federated identity and access control model for this interaction, independent of a specific vendor implementation and consistent with the federated identity and access control mechanisms defined in the EU-DREAM Data Platform. This three-stage pattern is used whenever user or service interaction with the platform occurs [18].

Sign-in Flow

The sign-in flow begins when the user opens a client application and tries to use a feature that requires authentication. The app then sends a request for this protected resource to the EU-DREAM API Gateway (see Figure 17).

The gateway inspects the request and sees that no valid login information is attached, so it cannot assume who the user is and does not grant access. Instead, it starts the OIDC sign-in procedure. To continue, the gateway returns a *302 redirect* to the client, pointing to the IdP. This redirect already contains an OIDC authorisation request; the client follows this redirect and sends the user to the IdP.

The IdP displays a login page; the user enters their credentials, and the IdP checks them. If the login fails, the IdP returns an error, and the flow stops. If it succeeds, the user is now authenticated with the IdP, but the gateway still has no access token.

As the last step of this flow, the IdP sends the browser back to the gateway with another *302 redirect*. This second redirect contains a short-lived authorisation code. The browser follows the redirect, and the gateway receives this code on its dedicated callback endpoint. At this point, the user is authenticated at the IdP, and the gateway holds a code that it will use in the next flow to obtain tokens.

Figure 17: OIDC sign-in flow between the Client Application, the EU-DREAM API Gateway and the Identity Provider, ending with the user authenticated at the IdP and the gateway holding an authorisation code but no access token yet.

Access Flow

The access flow starts when the API Gateway receives the redirect with the authorisation code. The goal of this flow is to exchange the code for tokens and use those tokens when calling EU-DREAM services on behalf of the user.

First, the gateway opens a connection to the IdP. It sends a token request that includes the authorisation code and its own client credentials. The IdP validates the code and checks the client credentials.

If all checks pass, the IdP responds with an access token, which encodes what the client is allowed to do, then with an ID token, which describes who the user is. These tokens are usually JSON Web Tokens (JWTs). A JWT is a compact string that contains claims such as user ID, roles, and scopes, and includes a digital signature that allows the receiver to verify that the IdP issued it and that it has not been modified [30].

The gateway validates the access token. It checks the signature; if anything is wrong, the token is rejected, and no call is made to the services. If everything is correct, the token is accepted and associated with the current caller.

When the client sends an API call, the gateway uses the validated token, builds a security context with user identity, roles and scopes, adds this context as headers or metadata, and forwards the request to the correct EU-DREAM service.

Figure 18 visualises these steps, from receiving the authorisation code to forwarding an authenticated request to a backend service.

Figure 18: Access Flow, Token exchange and authorised access

Session Flow

After the first login and token exchange, the user is already known to the platform. The session flow explains what happens with the many follow-up requests that come while the user continues to use the application. The goal is to avoid repeating the complete sign-in and access flow each time, while still ensuring the session is valid [30].

Once the first access token has been obtained, the client application keeps a small proof of the login, which is a token that proves access rights, meaning that any party that holds it can use it, so it must be protected.

For each new call to a protected endpoint, the client sends its cookie or bearer token to the EU-DREAM API Gateway. When the gateway receives the request, it first validates the token. If the token is valid, the gateway rebuilds the security context from it. It then attaches this context to the internal request and forwards the call to the appropriate EU-DREAM service.

The length of time for which a token remains valid is not fixed; it is configured in the Identity Provider. In the case of EU-DREAM, this provider is Keycloak. Access tokens are short-lived and checked on every call; ID tokens are also short-lived and are mainly used immediately after login to identify the user. In contrast, refresh tokens or server-side sessions live longer, so new short-lived access tokens can be issued without asking the user to log in again.

In the EU-DREAM context, this means that a recently issued access token always backs every API call from the client toward any EU-DREAM service, and that long-running user sessions rely on controlled refresh logic or session cookies, not on never-expiring tokens. This is consistent with the zero-trust model, which assumes no long-term implicit trust.

In addition to token lifetimes, Keycloak also defines session policies. These settings ensure that users are periodically prompted to re-authenticate, even when refresh tokens are used.

If the session or token is no longer valid, the gateway rejects the request. This also guarantees that a fresh, verifiable authentication and authorisation are provided for every accepted request. It also means that, if a token is leaked or a session is compromised, the impact is limited in time by the configured lifetimes and session rules.

Figure 19 shows how valid sessions follow a fast path, validation and forwarding, and how expired or invalid sessions result in renewal through a new login or token refresh, depending on the configured policies.

Figure 19: Subsequent requests reuse a token, which the API Gateway validates before forwarding calls or restarting the sign-in flow

6.3. Kafka Security

This subsection explains how internal event traffic is protected. Apache Kafka is the central messaging backbone of the EU-DREAM platform. It connects the DT infrastructure to the Data Platform and carries orchestration events, data tasks, ingestion notifications, and other asynchronous workflows [4].

In practice, Kafka security in EU-DREAM relies on the following mechanisms [31] [32]:

- **Encrypted transport (TLS):** All traffic between Kafka brokers and clients uses TLS, so messages from DT and Data Platform services are encrypted in transit and cannot be read or modified by an attacker who can see the network traffic.

- **Client authentication (SASL/SCRAM)** – All producers and consumers authenticate over TLS with SASL/SCRAM. Each microservice has its own Kafka principal and password, managed centrally, so only authorised EU-DREAM services can connect.
- **ACL-based authorisation** – Kafka ACLs restrict what each principal can do on which topics, Orchestrator on *dt.orchestrator / dt.agent.**, ingestion services on *dp.ingestion.**.
- **Network isolation and topic namespaces** – Brokers are reachable only from inside the secure cluster. Network Policies and firewalls limit which namespaces may connect, and topic namespaces such as *dt.**, *dp.** and *integration.** separate responsibilities and simplify ACL management.

Together, these measures harden Kafka as a controlled backbone fully aligned with EU-DREAM's security-by-design [13]

6.4. Secrets Management

All these controls depend on reliable handling of passwords, keys and certificates. EU-DREAM uses a central secrets-management service based on Vault store, generates and delivers secrets securely, with policies and audit logs [24]:

- **Service credentials:** EU-DREAM components obtain Kafka logins, LL ingestion API keys and internal credentials from the vault instead of code or static config. Services authenticate with the vault and fetch secrets at runtime, simplifying rotation and reducing the risk of leaks.
- **Database access** – For databases on the data platform, the Database Secrets Engine issues short-lived per-service credentials and revokes them when their leases expire. This limits the impact of compromised passwords and supports.
- **API and encryption keys**– Vault stores API keys for external providers and manages cryptographic keys for encrypting data, signing JWT/OIDC tokens and computing hashes. With the Transit engine, applications send data to the vault for encryption, decryption, or signing, while the keys never leave the vault.
- **Policies and audit** – Access to secrets is controlled by policies bound to service identities; each component sees only its own secrets, and all access is logged.

In this way, secrets management becomes a core infrastructure function, underpinning Kafka hardening, database and API security, and cryptography in a consistent and replicable way.

6.5. Coverage of security requirements

This subsection summarises how the security mechanisms implemented in the EU-DREAM Data Management Platform fulfil the main security requirements applicable to Task 3.4, as described in this deliverable. It focuses on requirements related to the GDPR, privacy by design, controlled access to datasets, encryption, identity and access management, and secure secret handling.

First, the platform must guarantee that data and key transactions cannot be modified without authorisation. This is achieved through the DLT Interface and the Trusted Data Exchange Layer,

which compute Merkle trees on selected datasets, anchor only the Merkle roots on a permissioned blockchain and keep all raw data in the Data Platform.

Any change in anchored data can later be detected by recomputing the root and comparing it with the on-chain value, so the DLT acts as an integrity layer on top of storage services [13].

Second, access to datasets always passes through Keycloak and the API Gateway using tokens and roles, and privacy-sensitive flows. Vault reduces the exposure of credentials and encryption keys by managing them centrally and by avoiding secrets in code or static configuration [24].

Third, access to datasets is restricted to authorised users and services with differentiated permissions. Keycloak provides identity and access management, issues OAuth2/OIDC tokens and encodes roles and scopes. The API Gateway validates these tokens on every call and enforces role-based policies, services and southbound connectors authenticate in the same way or via mutual TLS. Vault policies are bound to service identities, so each microservice sees only the secrets required for its function, implementing least privilege across the platform [17] [19] [24].

Finally, the security model must support encryption, auditability and scalability across environments and Living Labs. External and critical internal traffic is protected with TLS or mTLS, the vault encrypts stored secrets and provides a Transit engine for application-level encryption.

Table 9 below summarises this mapping between the main security requirements and the mechanisms used to implement them in the EU-DREAM Data Management Platform.

Security requirement	Main mechanisms
GDPR compliance and privacy-by-design	Personal and operational data remain off-chain in controlled databases; only hashes and identifiers are stored on the DLT. All access to these datasets passes through the IAM and API Gateway, with secrets and keys managed centrally in a vault.
Only authorised users/services may access datasets, differentiated access via IAM.	Keycloak provides identities, roles, and OAuth2/OIDC tokens; the API Gateway verifies these tokens on every call before routing requests; and Vault policies are bound to service identities so that each component receives only the secrets it needs.
Capability to encrypt data when appropriate	External and sensitive internal traffic is protected with TLS or mutual TLS; Vault encrypts stored secrets and provides the Transit engine for application-level encryption; and databases or volumes can use encryption at rest with keys managed by Vault.
Auditability and traceability of security-relevant actions	Anchoring events on the DLT creates immutable records; Vault logs every secret access and lease event; and GitLab CI/CD, the API Gateway, and Kafka provide deployment and access logs that together form a coherent audit trail.
Scalable and modular security controls across LLs and environments	Security components such as the API Gateway, IAM, Vault, Kafka and DLTi are deployed as containers, orchestrated by Docker Compose in Dev/Preprod and by Kubernetes in Prod, so that the same security patterns can be reused.

Table 9: Mapping between key security requirements and implementation mechanisms

7. Conclusions

This deliverable demonstrates how Task 3.4 transforms the EU-DREAM Data Management Platform from a high-level architecture into an operational, secure, and replicable solution that can run across heterogeneous Living Labs. It connects the system view and modular platform principles from WP1 with the Digital Twin, AI, and NLP developments in WP2, and with the data governance and interoperability work of WP3, providing the concrete platform on which WP4 services and WP7 validations can rely.

It defines the roles and interfaces of the EU-DREAM components and maps them onto a hybrid cloud-edge infrastructure with three controlled environments: development, pre-production and production. Then, it formalises a common devops stack based on GitLab CI/CD, Docker, Docker Compose, Kubernetes, and Vault, so that every component follows the same build, test, and deployment path across all environments and living labs. Moreover, it embeds a zero-trust security model through IAM, API Gateway, Kafka hardening, secrets management, and DLT-based integrity, ensuring interoperability and scalability without weakening privacy, compliance, or trust.

8. References

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